

**METHODS OF CLINICAL EXAMINATION IN THE COMPARISON OF
CONSTRUCTIONS OF FULL DENTURES.**

Ruziyeva Sitora Sapar qizi

Tashkent medical academy, Assistant of the department
Dentistry and maxillofacial surgery

Abstract: This article was developed to prevent the inconveniences caused by prosthodontics of patients with complete loss of teeth with orthopedic fully removable prostheses. In this case, prostheses of two different constructions, i.e., the edge of the prostheses base has a wide volume and the traditional Prostheses without a wide margin of the prosthesis base were recommended to patients and compared using several methods. In this, patients were asked to fill out a questionnaire, speech tests and stereognosis methods were used. As a result, it was found that prostheses with a wide margin of the prosthesis base are more effective.

Key words: dent facial system, temporomandibular joint, occlusal, seat upper denture, and seat lower denture.

Introduction: Full dentures also called a complete denture; this appliance replaces an entire arch of missing teeth. A full denture rests atop your gums and relies on your palate (the roof of your mouth) or lower jawbone ridge for support. You may need to use denture adhesive (a special type of glue) to keep your appliance firmly in place. Full dentures are likely what come to mind when you think about traditional dentures. They consist of artificial teeth and a gum-colored base. People who wear dentures usually take them out at night to clean them and give their gums a rest.

Materials and methods:

In accordance with the purpose and objectives of the work, a total of 16 patients (8 men and 8 women) were examined and treated in aged 45-75 years. The identification of age groups (Table 1) was carried out in accordance with WHO recommendations.

Table 1.

Age	Patients	Main group (n=8)		Control group (n=8)	
		M	F	M	F
45-59(average)	2		1		1
60-75(elderly)	10	3	2	3	2
75 и (old people)	4	1	1	1	1
total	16	4	4	4	4

All 16 supervised patients, depending on the method of constructing removable dentures, were divided into the following groups: two main groups and a control group for comparison. The comparison group (control) consisted of 8 patients who received traditional orthopedic treatment. The main group, consisting of 8 patients, had dentures constructed in the “HANAU” articulator, who had significant atrophy of the alveolar processes of the lower jaw; volumetric modeling was used in combination with calotte placement of teeth. In addition, when conducting stereognosis (determination of tactile sensitivity in the oral cavity) it was necessary to obtain initial indicative data.

Clinical examination. All patients underwent a detailed examination using generally accepted clinical methods, study of control diagnostic models. When examining edentulous patients, we took as a basis the requirements of the protocol,

- Nosological form: loss of teeth due to an accident or their removal for other reasons.

- Complete absence of teeth on one or both jaws.
- Change in facial configuration (lip retraction).
- Pronounced nasolabial and chin folds, drooping corners of the mouth.
- Reduction in the size of the lower third of the face.
- Absence of exostoses.

- Absence of pronounced atrophy of the alveolar process (in the complete absence of teeth on one or both jaws; in the complete absence teeth on the upper jaw -

Schroeder's classification, with complete absence of teeth on the lower jaw - Keller's classification).

- Healthy oral mucosa (moderately pliable, moderately mobile, pale pink in color, moderately secretes mucous secretion, Supplee class).

- Absence of diseases of the oral mucosa.

- Absence of pronounced pathology of the temporomandibular joint.

When collecting anamnesis, the time and causes of tooth loss, whether the patient has previously used removable dentures, and whether there is an allergic background.

Result and discussion:

Complaints of pain and discomfort in the temporomandibular joint were targeted. A detailed clinical assessment was carried out: the appearance of the face, the presence of its asymmetry, the severity of nasolabial and mental folds, the nature of the closure of the lips, the presence of cracks and macerations in the corners of the mouth, the degree of its opening, the smoothness and direction of movements of the lower jaw; mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed (color, moisture and integrity, relief, the degree of its pliability in various areas, the presence of a “dangling ridge”), the severity and location of the frenulum and cheek folds; the depth of the vault of the hard palate, the severity of the alveolar processes, the shape of their slopes and other conditions for possible anatomical retention.

In the lower jaw, attention was also paid to the presence and severity of the internal oblique line or other bony protrusions, and the state of tone of the muscles of the floor of the mouth (weak, moderate, pronounced). Particular attention was paid to the position of the transitional fold, mucous tubercles, as well as a thorough study of the sublingual area. At the same time, we distinguished the anterior and lateral sections of the sublingual space.

The severity of the anterior sublingual space may be different depending on the degree of atrophy of the alveolar process, the size of the sublingual salivary glands, and the position of the tongue. The lateral section of the sublingual space, extending

from the canines to the anterior border of the mucous tubercles, is a gap between the tongue and the inner surface of the alveolar process.

The depth of the floor of the mouth depends on the position of the tongue during movement of which changes the size of the anterior section sublingual space. With a half-open mouth and normal position of the tongue, the width of the space is 4-5 mm; with the tongue in the posterior position, this area becomes more voluminous in the sagittal direction, amounting to 8-10 mm. When the tongue moves forward, the anterior section of the sublingual space turns into a narrow gap.

Possibility of expanding the base in the anterior vestibule of the mouth determined purely individually. The patient is asked not to tense his lips and keep the lower jaw at rest. The doctor then places the index finger in the middle of the lower lip on the inside and the thumb on the outside and asks the patient to purse the lips. This zone has an oval shape and, starting from the midline, gradually narrowing, ends between the canines and the first premolars, where a powerful muscle unit is located.

Additional landmarks were used to set the anterior teeth of the upper jaw. Distance from the labial surface of the incisors to papilla incisiva is 8.0 ± 1.0 mm; the labial surface of the canine is located at a distance of 10.0 ± 1.0 mm from the edge of the first palatal fold. The tops of the canines lie on the SRS - Linie (SRS line, that is, caninus-papilla-caninus).

Conclusions:

When characterizing the edentulous upper and lower jaws, we used the Schroeder and Keller classifications, respectively. The condition and pliability of the mucous membrane covering the prosthetic bed was determined taking into account the Supplee classification. Some special methods and information, in addition to the medical history, were entered into the card we developed. In accordance with the principle of informed consent, the patient was provided with detailed information about the treatment plan and supervision features. A special role was given to the psychological preparation of patients before prosthetics.

References

1. Türk B, Ünsal Ö, Kaya KS, Coşkun BU. Dislocated Dental Prosthesis Sitting at the Larynx in an Aphasic Patient: Potentially Fatal Situation. *J Craniofac Surg.* 2017 Oct;28(7):e655-e657. doi: 10.1097/SCS.0000000000003795. PMID: 28872495.
2. Dholam KP, Singh GP, Sathaye N, Gurav SV, Shinde A. Two-piece oral facial prosthesis retained with magnets for a complex maxillary facial defect: A clinical report. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2022 Dec;128(6):1365-1368. doi: 10.1016/j.prosdent.2021.03.014. Epub 2021 Jun 8. PMID: 34112522.
3. Saccomanno S, Mummolo S, Giancaspro S, Manenti RJ, Mastrapasqua RF, Marzo G, Quinzi V. Catering Work Profession and Medico-Oral Health: A Study on 603 Subjects. *Healthcare (Basel).* 2021 May 13;9(5):582. doi: 10.3390/healthcare9050582. PMID: 34068356; PMCID: PMC8153258.
4. Dholam KP, Singh GP, Sathaye N, Gurav SV, Shinde A. Two-piece oral facial prosthesis retained with magnets for a complex maxillary facial defect: A clinical report. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2022 Dec;128(6):1365-1368. doi: 10.1016/j.prosdent.2021.03.014. Epub 2021 Jun 8. PMID: 34112522.
5. Shemetov, O.S. Methods for assessing the quality of complete removable dentures / O.S. Shemetov, V.A. Bondaletov, E.B. Tumakova // *Ukrainian Dental Almanac.* - 2010.- No. 4. - P. 95-96.
6. 101. Shemetov, O.S. Assessment of the quality of prosthetics with complete removable dentures in a clinical setting / O.S. Shemetov, L.A. Lugovaya, H.A. Ryabushko, P.V. Kuts // *Ukrainian Dental Almanac.* - 2014.-№2.
7. 102. Shemonaev, V.I. Method for determining the prosthetic plane using lateral teleroentgenograms/ V.I. Shemonaev, I.Yu. Pchelin, E.A. Buyanov, O.V. Sharanovskaya // *Fundamental Research.* - 2014. - No. 10-8.-S. 95-99.
8. 103. Curtain. A.A. Factors influencing the lifespan of complete removable dentures / A.A. Curtain // *Institute of Dentistry.* - 2009. - No. 1. -P.52-53.

9. Tlustenko, B.C. Improving orthopedic treatment of patients with complete absence of teeth with a pronounced prognic ratio of toothless jaws [Text]: abstract. dis. Ph.D. honey. Sciences / B.C. Tlustenko. - Samara, 2009. - 22 p.
10. 92. Khvatova, V. A. Clinical gnathology / V. A. Khvatova. -M.: Medicine, 2005.-296 p.
11. 93. Hanning, V. Modern prosthetic technologies Text. / W. Hanning. - Berlin, 2004.-281 p.